

Spatio-Temporal Analysis of Malaria Cases in Ghana:

Development of an Interactive Dashboard for Public Health Decision-Making

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This work was completed as part of the MSc program in Geoinformatics and Spatial Data Science at the University of Münster. The dashboard and analysis are intended for research and educational use, with the goal of supporting malaria control efforts in Ghana.

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1.0 Introduction

In Ghana, malaria continues to be a major public health issue, as different regions and time periods may lead to changes in how malaria spreads. The analysis utilizes subnational malaria incidence data spanning 2010–2020, with 2012 serving as the primary intervention year for comparative assessment. By using Geographic Information Systems (GIS) technology and spatial analysis to understand the spaced incidence patterns of malaria, we can assess how well anti-malarial treatments such as insecticide-treated nets (ITNs) and Indoor Residual Sprayings (IRS) work at preventing diseases from being transmitted through mosquitoes. To aid public health officials in identifying high risk areas, tracking the success of their interventions, and optimising resource allocation, we combined subnational epidemiological information and interactive visualization tools to create an online Dashboard specifically designed for them.

1.1 Goals

- **Identify high-risk areas:** Map malaria hotspots over time to guide resource prioritization.
- **Measure intervention change:** Compare changes in malaria prevalence before and after interventions.
- **Offer real-time insights:** Allow users to map trends, correlations, and spatial relationships on an interactive dashboard.

1.2 Personas – Target User Groups

- **Dr. Grace Mensah (Public Health Specialist)**
 - Needs current and accurate data for appropriate resource allocation.
 - Needs tools to show temporal variation trends and intervention impacts on malaria.
- **Abena Osei (Community Health Worker):**
 - Requires mobile-friendly tools to identify high-risk areas and notify communities.
 - Requires alerts about real-time population data and places where there is an outbreak of malaria.

1.3 User Stories

1.3.1 Identifying High-Risk Areas

As Dr. Grace Mensah,

I would like to map malaria hotspots on a map for the past five years so that I can prioritize the allocation of resources to the most affected areas.

1.3.2 Monitoring Intervention Effectiveness

As Dr. Grace Mensah,

I need to know the malaria incidence rates before and after distribution of bed nets so that I may be able to assess the performance of the intervention.

1.3.3 Real-Time Risk Alerts

As Abena Osei,

I would also like real-time alerts sent to me when locations become more at risk for malaria, so I can do community outreach there first.

1.3.4 Understanding Seasonal Pattern

Being Abena Osei,

I would like to understand how rainfall and temperature correlate with malaria outbreaks to educate the community about preventive measures before the rainy season.

2.0 Design Rationale

The project design of the app was obtained through the requirements of user groups and what tasks they are trying to perform. Important design principles include:

2.1 Visualization Design

- **Temporal Trends:** Line graphs were selected to depict the time-trend changes in malaria incidence and treatment rates to allow users to see the effect of their interventions.
- **Spatial Hotspots:** Interactive choropleth maps were implemented to visualize malaria incidence by region and allow users to know the areas at the highest risk.
- **Comparison Dashboard:** Bar charts and faceted maps were used to illustrate malaria incidence before and after interventions so users could see the differentiating effect of interventions.

2.2 Interaction Design

- **Real-Time Exploration:** The Shiny dashboard allows users to explore the data interactively by filtering for individual years, measures, and regions.
- **Dynamic Alerts:** Dynamic alerts are another aspect built into the design-but only for future versions of the app-which would enable the user to be informed of emerging hotspots in real-time.
- **User-Centric Design:** The dashboard is designed with easy-to-learn controls and easily accessible visuals that should enable non-computer literate users to navigate the dashboard with good usability.

Figure 1 Malaria Spatio-Temporal Dashboard

2.3 Alignment with Persona Needs

- **Dr. Grace Mensah:** Dashboard containing insights on trends, evaluation of interventions, and effective resource allocation.
- **Abena Osei:** Interactive maps and real-time insights into community outreach and educational campaigns.

3.0 Project Description

The project offers an interactive dashboard to analyze spatio-temporal trends with respect to malaria incidence and the effectiveness of interventions in Ghana. Data is acquired through different sources covering incidence, intervention coverage, and treatment effectiveness.

3.1 Functionality

- **Interactive Map:** The map shows the malaria incidence and intervention effectiveness for a selected region-wise year.
- **Temporal Trends:** Generate time series plots of malaria incidence and treatment rates over varying time intervals.
- **Comparison Dashboard:** The bar chart with faceted maps allows for comparison of malaria incidence before and after intervention.
- **Spatial Analysis:** Tools for hotspot identification, spatial autocorrelation (Moran's I), and variogram analysis.
- **Data Table:** Provides easy and sortable access to region and time-year malaria data.

3.2 Planned vs. Realized Features

Table 1 Planned vs Realized Features

Feature	Planned	Realized
Interactive Map	Yes	Yes
Temporal Trends	Yes	Yes
Comparison Dashboard	Yes	Yes
Spatial Autocorrelation	Yes	Yes
Real-Time Alerts	Yes	No
Mobile-Friendly Interface	Yes	No

3.3 Git Repository

The code and data for this project can be found in this Github repository:

<https://github.com/jprincegh/Spatio-temporal-Analysis-of-Data-in-R/tree/main>

3.4 Docker Image

The application is available as a Docker image ([Click Here](#)). Run the following commands to access the dashboard locally:

```
docker pull iprince/malariaanalysisgh-dashboard
docker run -d --rm -p 3838:3838 iprince/malariaanalysisgh-dashboard
```

4.0 Analysis Processes

The proposed step-by-step analytical procedure started at data gathering, preparation and ended up in spatial modeling. Here is a more elaborate discussion of individual steps involved:

4.1. Data Preparation and Cleaning

- **Data Sources:**
 - Subnational unit-level malaria incidence data from the Malaria Atlas Project.
 - Intervention data on bed net coverage and use and indoor residual spraying.
 - Treatment data: Metrics on effective treatment rates.
 - Ghana shapefile: Used GIS data of Ghana administrative regions.
- **Data Cleaning:**
 - Removing extra spaces and renaming columns for uniformity.
 - Dealing with missing values mostly by filtering incomplete records out.
 - Aggregated malaria incidence by region and year for hotspot analysis.
- **Data Merging:**
 - Stacking malaria incidence, intervention, and treatment data for a single dataset
 - Merging the combined dataset with Ghana shapefile for spatio-analysis.

4.2 Exploratory Analysis

- **Descriptive Statistics:**
 - Described malaria incidence and treatment data, which provided an understanding of the overall trends.
- **Temporal Trends:**
 - Line graphs represent changes in time to malaria incidence and treatment rates.
 - Interactive visualization using ggplot2 and plotly.

Figure 2 Temporal Trends

- **Spatial Trends:**
 - To visualize malaria incidence by region, choropleth maps were created.
 - Interactive maps created with tmap and leaflet.

4.3 Hotspot Identification

- **Aggregation:**
 - Average malaria incidence by region and year was calculated.
- **Visualization:**
 - Interactive maps showing on malaria hotspots on select years (2015 used in the project).

Figure 3 Malaria Hotspots in Ghana, Year = 2015

4.4 Impact of Interventions

- **Comparison of Periods:**
 - Calculated average malaria incidence before and after the intervention year (2012).
 - Observed changes on treatment coverage and malaria incidence.

- **Visualization:**

- Bar charts with a faceted map comparison of intervention periods.

Figure 4 Comparison of Malaria Incidence Bar Chart

Figure 5 Comparison of Malaria Incidence faceted Map

4.5 Spatial Correlation and Modeling

- **Spatial Autocorrelation:**

- Moran's I test for global spatial dependencies.
- Local Moran's I analysis in looking for spatial clusters with high/low incidences.

```
Moran I test under randomisation
data: values
weights: lw
Moran I statistic standard deviate = 0.36271, p-value = 0.3584
alternative hypothesis: greater
sample estimates:
Moran I statistic      Expectation      Variance
-7.812767e-04         -3.484321e-03      5.553676e-05
```

Figure 6 Moran I Test Under Randomization

- **Variogram Analysis:**

- Fitted a variogram model for spatial dependence analysis.

```
> # Fit variogram model
> model_initial <- vgm(psill = 8000, model = "Exp", range = 200, nugget = 1500)
> vm_fit <- fit.variogram(v.m, model = model_initial, fit.method = 6)
> print(vm_fit)
model    psill    range
1  Nug 14973.929  0.0000
2  Exp 2932.188 176.7804
```


Figure 7 Fitted Variogram Model

- **Spatial Lag Model:**

- How other regions influence the malaria incidence.
- Analyzed residuals and marginal effects for interventions.

```
Call: lagsarlm(formula = Value.x ~ Value.y + Region, data = ghana_sf, listw = lw)

Residuals:
    Min       1Q   Median       3Q      Max
-185.344  -91.307  -43.162   54.128  400.330

Type: lag
Coefficients: (asymptotic standard errors)
              Estimate Std. Error z value Pr(>|z|)
(Intercept)   580.70407   100.92678   5.7537 8.730e-09
Value.y       -1.04603     0.17244  -6.0660 1.311e-09
RegionAshanti -93.41626   16.85019  -5.5439 2.958e-08
RegionBono    -31.15066   16.53370  -1.8841 0.0595555
RegionBono East -46.36414   17.53948  -2.6434 0.0082074
RegionCentral -103.38708   23.47892  -4.4034 1.066e-05
RegionEastern -93.79402   23.59620  -3.9750 7.039e-05
RegionGreater Accra -212.54980   29.22659  -7.2725 3.531e-13
RegionNorthern -35.20786   16.49764  -2.1341 0.0328334
RegionNorthern East -68.37061   18.45836  -3.7040 0.0002122
RegionOti     -1.97326   16.97491  -0.1162 0.9074576
RegionSavannah -38.20218   16.68517  -2.2896 0.0220451
RegionUpper East -70.84247   19.32448  -3.6659 0.0002464
RegionUpper West -61.45077   18.76067  -3.2755 0.0010547
RegionVolta   -112.13159   23.22852  -4.8273 1.384e-06
RegionWestern -63.09964   16.66987  -3.7853 0.0001536
RegionWestern North  5.30617   17.18266   0.3088 0.7574666

Rho: -2.3168, LR test value: 6.1839, p-value: 0.012892
Asymptotic standard error: 0.66922
z-value: -3.4619, p-value: 0.0005363
Wald statistic: 11.985, p-value: 0.0005363

Log likelihood: -11710.29 for lag model
ML residual variance (sigma squared): 15807, (sigma: 125.73)
Number of observations: 1872
Number of parameters estimated: 19
AIC: 23459, (AIC for lm: 23463)
LM test for residual autocorrelation
test value: 4.14, p-value: 0.041882
```

Figure 9 Residual Effects

Figure 8 LISA (Local Moran's I)

4.6 Dashboard Development

- **Integration:**
 - Everything visualization and analysis in one package.
- **Interactivity:**
 - Year, metric, and region controls were included.
 - Maps and charts will update in real-time.

Figure 10 Application Dashboard

5.0 Reflection and Discussion

The newly built-up dashboard includes interactive visualization and spatially recognised data and can be used effectively to monitor malaria disease trends or incidences in Ghana. This is achieved through an analysis of spatial autocorrelation and the present-day view of the user regarding current malaria incidence. The main weaknesses are both the non-availability of real-time alerts for alerts and the impenetrability of the dashboard for mobile devices for use by field workers or personnel in Ghana. Areas of future enhancement should involve integrating environmental data with indicators and eventually deploying the application via the cloud to reach a much wider audience.

5.1 Evaluation of the Final Product

The evaluation conducted on the final product against the project's key objectives provided a look into both the strengths and weaknesses of the solutions provided by the dashboard. The dashboard was very strong in that it had an interactive ability to represent the trend of malaria over time and allowed for the comparison of the effect of the interventions on malaria rates. The graphics of the data were intended for non-experts so that they could interpret complex spatial data in a user-friendly method. The use of specialized tools, such as Moran's I and the variogram, increased the level of analytical sophistication available to the user.

There were, however, several identified weaknesses. The dashboard currently does not provide a mechanism for the user to receive a real-time alert if there is a reported case of an outbreak; therefore, this would reduce the dashboard's value for an outbreak.

Additionally, the interface is not entirely mobile-friendly and, therefore, does not allow access for field personnel working in areas that are remote. Lastly, the analytical capacity of the dashboard may be improved by integrating additional environmental variables (for example, rainfall or temperature) to provide an improved interpretation of the malaria transmission process.

5.2 What Could Have Been Done Better

There are multiple areas that need to be improved upon to produce a highly successful development process. Providing a real-time alert system would allow for community health workers to receive immediate alerts concerning areas of increased viral activity. Increased focus on making mobile applications accessible via smartphones would give field workers greater access to the program and enable them to conduct their data collection and community surveillance more efficiently. By conducting formal user testing with appropriate types of stakeholders, including public health experts and community health workers, designers would have gained invaluable input regarding how the product could be enhanced through improvements to the user interface and overall functionality.

5.3 What Worked Well

Several main objectives were accomplished through this project. Users now have access to a dynamic analytic dashboard with all primary datasets combined into a single location for analysis. Interactive visualisation elements, for example, a range of leaflet maps and plotly graph options have helped with user interaction while encouraging exploration of the data via interaction with visualisation tools. Several spatial analytics toolsets and techniques showed how geographical information systems can provide powerful insights into patterns associated with malaria, including distribution and impacts of interventions. The project illustrated the strong contribution of these geospatial techniques to the decision-maker's ability to make better public health decisions.

6.0 Limitation and Future Improvements

Although this dashboard is a strong tool for understanding how things look on a desktop, there are limitations related to its use in the field and the extent of analysis possible. Currently, data is outdated (static) and requires manual uploading to keep updated instead of using live data feeds to allow for real-time analysis. Also, the interface is only partially mobile-responsive, which limits access for community health teams in underserved areas. Furthermore, it does not include a built-in alerting capability for early detection of outbreaks. Finally, from the perspective of understanding malaria transmission better and being able to use the model's results as a prediction tool and to better understand the seasonal status of malaria transmission dynamics, it does not yet include environmental factors like rain and temperature, which impact the malaria transmission process.

The gaps identified in the current version of the application will be addressed through a phased development approach. Short-term objectives will include improving mobile versions of applications to facilitate field deployment of new features; building APIs to provide users with up-to-date information in real time; and adding environmental factors

from satellite imagery and local weather reports. Intermediate priorities will include developing predictive modelling tools to assist users in forecasting future health events; establishing a secure multi-user logon for authorized users; and improving the export functionality of reports, maps, etc., so that the application can support operational reporting functions more efficiently. Long-term objectives will be to combine the Tool with other national health information systems; extend use of the Tool to additional categories of disease surveillance; and convert the tool's technical architecture to a cloud-based solution for greater availability, dependability, and ability to receive continuous improvements.

7.0 Implications and Applications

This tool provides public health organisations with a method through which they can base their allocation of resources to combat malaria not only in a timely way but also make targeted decisions. Additionally, it will provide an effective mechanism for monitoring and evaluating the impact of malaria control programmes over time and place, as well as provide the basis for developing a framework that can be utilized to develop an early warning system that will alert authorities to potential malaria outbreaks by detecting anomalies in spatial and temporal trends. The geospatial science community will be able to see, through this project, how a combination of advanced spatial analysis techniques (e.g., spatial autocorrelation, variogram modelling, and interactive web mapping) can be seamlessly integrated into one consistent and reproducible workflow. The project will serve as an applied example of how to perform spatial epidemiology and use free and open-source tools for conducting meaningful spatial health analysis.

The findings demonstrate the importance of creating and developing an open-source platform using a user-centred approach for low-resourced areas. It has a modular, scalable architecture which is flexible enough to allow other surveillance systems to be built on top of it, and used in multiple countries and health systems, creating opportunities for collaboration and building reservoir capability in digital health.

8.0 Conclusion

Geospatial data science strategies have been successfully applied for malaria surveillance in Ghana. The dashboard that was been created serves as a complete analysis tool that combines spatial statistics, time-based analysis, and interactive visualisation. As core objectives were met through the creation of the dashboard, the experience highlighted real-world challenges and opportunities associated with developing data-driven public health solutions. This project advances the development of spatial analysis methodology and produces real-world applications related to disease surveillance and the potential for adapting the technology for other disease monitoring and mapping applications in public health.

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